

An Empirical Study on Organizational Climate in Neycer India Limited, Vadalur

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ABSTRACT

Organizational climate is nothing but its work environment as perceived by the individuals in the organization. Climate is the manifested in the observable routines and reward of organization. Many organisations are realized that human resources are of one of the important source of competitive advantage and sustaining of the organisation for a long term. It is evidenced that organizational climate plays a positive role in exerting greater efforts from the employees. Thus, positive organisational climate can be created with the help of organisational climate intervention. This study investigates the prevailing organisational climate in Neycer India Limited, Vadalur of Tamil Nadu State and to identify the variations in perception on organisational climate based on certain selective demographic characteristics. The results of the empirical analysis have been discussed in this article.

Keywords: *Co-workers relationships, Organisational Climate, Organisational Design, Reward system, Work environment*

INTRODUCTION

Organizational climate is nothing but its work environment as perceived by the individuals in the organization. Climate is the manifested in the observable routines and reward of organization. The routines are the event and practice of an organization while rewards pertain to what behaviours get acknowledged and supported. Organizational climate is the process of quantifying culture of an organization. It strongly influences the functions of

the staff and job performance. It's also called corporate climate.

The phrase "organizational climate" refers to working in an area or office where many of the other workers are very organized. Organized people like to work with other organization. It is a set of properties of the work environment perceived directly or indirectly by the employee that is assumed to be a major force in influencing employee behavior. Climate and culture are both important aspects of the overall context, environment or situation.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

For the purposes of present investigation, definitions by Gerber (2003) and Moran and Volkwein(1992) were integrated. Organisational climate is defined as the shared perceptions, feelings and attitudes that organisational members have about the fundamental elements of the organisation, which reflect the established norms, values and attitudes of the organisation's culture and influences individuals' behaviour positively or negatively. Organizational climate has been defined as a perception of the psychologically important aspects of the work environment and is recognized as a potential influence on employees' workplace behavior and job satisfaction (Ashforth, 1985). Climate consists of a set of characteristics that describe an organization, distinguish it from other organizations, are relatively enduring over time and influence the behavior of people in it. The individual worker's perception of his

work environment rather than a consensus view is considered, as different individuals may perceive the same workplace in different ways (Klien K. J., 2001). Organizational climate is defined as shared perceptions or prevailing organizational norms for conducting workplace activities (Reichers&schneider, 1990). It has been conceptualized as a cognitively based set of perceptual descriptions that define the psychological climate (Jones, 1984), and therefore it is possible to measure individual-level perceptions of the organizational climate for updating (Kozlowski&Hults, 1987). So the focus is on employees' perceptions of salient features of the organizational context. Kozlowski (1988) recommended that research consider the interaction between individual characteristics and perceived situational features of the environment when determining whether technical professionals will voluntarily seek to learn new skills. Perceptions relevant to a specific climate domain such as the innovation climate have motivational implications on congruent behavioral outcomes (Schneider, 1983). According to Campbellet, (1970)organizational climate is defined as a set of attributes specific to a particular organization that may be induced from the way that organization deals with its members and its environment. For the individual members within the organization, climate takes the form of a set of attitudes and experiences which describe the organization in terms of both static characteristics (such as degree of autonomy) and behavior outcome. Neelameham(2013) in his study found that the relation between demographic variables and organisational climate of a cement company, found no significant influence of religion on overall organisational climate. Verghese Singh &Verma(2010) studied the relation between customer orientation and organizational climate from a sample of 500 employees in public sector and private sector banks and arrived at a conclusion that organizational climate enhances with customer orientation. Higher customer orientation is conducive for building a sound organizational climate. Srivastav(2009) investigated organizational climate by measuring six climate motives on 453 executives in a large Indian public sector industry using motivational analysis of organizational climate. The findings demonstrate the heterogeneous nature of organizational climate, and the study helps to provide a better appreciation of differences in employee behavior across the company. Schulte (2006) conducted a research, which demonstrated that both individual-level climate

perceptions and organizational climate are related to job satisfaction and examined the overall climate in a work unit has significant influence on individual attitudes, after accounting for individuals' idiosyncratic perceptions of the climate. Smit,Collins & Clark (2005) suggested that an organization's climate plays a strategic role in knowledge creation capability. Patterson,Warr& West (2004) predicted that associations between company climate and productivity would be mediated by average level of job satisfaction by studying 42 manufacturing companies and interpreted that company productivity was more strongly correlated with those aspects of climate that had stronger satisfaction loadings. The study with regard to hotel industry of Davidson (2000) for the influence of demographics on organisational climate found no influence of gender.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Human Resource Development becomes crucial for organizational dynamism and performance. A positive climate is essential for the development and success of any organization. The present trend of privatization and globalization led to the manufacturing units facing cut throat competition. The survival and success of manufacturing units rest on the better utilization of human resources at their organizations. The units which provide better organizational climate to their employees achieve a lot compared to other organizations. The organizational climate influences the organizational productivity and well-being by influencing organizational processes such as problem solving, decision making, communicating and coordinating, individual process of learning and levels of motivation.

Organisational climate affects every activity in an organization directly or indirectly. The growth of an organization is directly related to the climate. One of the key factors that may influence on employees' perception is organisational climate. Organisational climate helps to set the quality of the organization. The present study makes an attempt to examine the organizational climate prevailing in Neycer India Limited through the organizational climate dimensions which are more widespread. It has been empirically proved in many Indian and Western organizations that employee-centered climate and achievement oriented climate ultimately improve performance. In this context, it seems sensible to undertake an investigation into organizational climate.

The valid conclusions based on such an investigation would result in developing suggestions for bringing about a organizational design, reward system, co-workers relationship, work environment, organizational commitment, communication and technology are essential for scaling new heights in employee productivity in Neycer India Limited. Further it encourages thinking among researchers on dimensions to be incorporated in a study of organizational climate.

The management of the manufacturing units concentrates on their organizational performance with the absence of better organizational climate. Even though, it may produce better results at the short run, the long run performance may be affected by the poor organizational climate. Till recently, the Human Resource experts have concentrated only on efficiency of manpower in the various industries, ignoring the continuous appraisal of organizational climate provided in the Industries. Therefore, it had a negative impact on productivity and profitability of the industries. Hence, the researcher has made an attempt to have an in depth analysis on these aspects.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

For the success of any organization there should be a good organizational climate. The perceived organizational climate as a set of properties of the working environment is a mediating variable between organizational system and motivation. Ostroff (1993) suggests that the effectiveness of an organization depends on the behavior of the people within the organization, and the organizational context, which they create. An in-depth analysis of organizational climate may help an organization to become more productive and efficient. Considering the fact that ceramics manufacturing industry is a booming sector and provides maximum employment opportunities, so it is essential to build conducive organizational climate. Considering all these aspects the investigator felt the imperative need to study the organizational climate in Neycer India Limited.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To analyse the organizational climate in Neycer India Limited, Vadalur.
- To know the employees' level of perception towards organizational design, reward system, co-workers relationship, work environment, direct

supervision, organizational commitment, communication and technology.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study is both descriptive and analytical in nature. The study also intends to see the relationship between the perception of the respondents and selected demographic variables of the respondents namely, Age, Gender, Marital Status Educational Qualification, Designation. In order to achieve the purpose of the study a survey design is employed.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The population of the study consists of three cadres of permanent, temporary and contract employees, namely, Managers, Supervisors and operative employees known as Workers working in Neycer India Limited. As per the hierarchy, the Managers are superiors to supervisors and workers. The population of Managers, Supervisors, and Workers of the three categories in Neycer India Limited is 267(153 Permanent Employees and 114 Temporary and Contract Employees).

SAMPLE SIZE

As the study organization is medium size and has minimum number of permanent employees, it is decided to choose the entire permanent employees of this organization as sample for this study. So the study comprises of the entire permanent employees of different hierarchy.

Sampling technique adopted in this study is stratified sampling. The research has been carried out with the sample size of 120, which includes different level of employees of Neycer India Limited.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the description of the demographic variables of the chosen employees for this study and inferential statistics with respect to their perception towards the climate of their organisation.

I: Description of the Demographic Variables of the Respondents

Table I: Distribution of Respondents according to their Demographic Variables

Personal Details		Frequency	Per cent
Age	Below 30 years	53	44.2
	30-35 years	41	34.2
	36-40 years	14	11.7
	Above 40 years	12	10.0
Gender	Male	106	88.3
	Female	14	11.7
Marital status	Married	88	73.3
	Unmarried	32	26.7
Educational Qualification	HSC & below	85	70.8
	ITI/Diploma	15	12.5
	UG/PG	13	10.8
	Others	7	5.8
Designation	Manager	9	7.5
	Supervisor	14	11.7
	Worker	97	80.8

It is known from the **Table I** that 44.2% of the respondents belong to the age group of below 30 years, 34.2% of the respondents belong to the age group of 30-35 years, 11.7% of the respondents belong to the age group of 36-40 years and remaining

10% of the respondents belong to the age group of above 40 years. It is found that majority of the respondents belong to the age group of below 30 years. Gender wise distribution of the respondents shows that 88.3% of the respondents are male respondents and 11.7% of the respondents are female respondents. It is found that majority of the respondents are male respondents.

Marital status wise distribution of the chosen respondents indicates that 73.3% of the respondents are married and 26.7 % of the respondents are unmarried respondents. It is found that majority of the respondents are married.

It is known from the educational qualification wise distribution of the respondents that 70.8% of the respondents having HSC & below HSC, 12.5% of the respondents having ITI/Diploma, 10.8% of the respondents having UG/PG degrees, and remaining 5.8% of the respondents having the educational qualifications Other than the above qualifications. It is found that majority of the respondents belong to HSC& below HSC category.

Designation wise distribution of the respondents indicates that 7.5 % of the respondents are managers, 11.7% of the respondents are supervisors and 80.8% of the respondents are workers. It is found that majority of the respondents chosen for the study is workers.

II: Employees' perception towards Organisational Climate of Neycer India Limited

Table II: Respondents' perception towards Organizational Design

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation
The organization's objectives are clear to me.	2.41	1.104
Employees have a clear understanding of what the organization is supposed to do.	2.69	1.129
Roles and responsibilities within the group are understood.	2.51	1.152
Clear reporting structures have been established in my organisation.	2.56	1.151
Employees in this organization have the right skill sets to perform their job.	2.74	1.041
Overall Mean/SD	2.582	1.115

Table II shows the respondents' perception towards Organizational Design available in their organization Neycer India Limited. The respondents are asked to rate their level of agreement towards Organizational Design in five point scale. Mean and standard

deviation values are calculated based on the collected data. The respondents have rated high for only two variables such as 'Employee in this organization have the right skill sets to perform their job' and 'Employees have a clear understanding of what the

organizations is supposed to do' they have rated very low for rest of the variables pertaining to Organizational Design of their organization. Further it is found from the Table 4.10 that the overall perception of the respondents towards the Organizational Design is below average.

Table III: Respondents' Perception towards Reward System

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation
Good work is recognized appropriately.	2.51	1.061
I receive an appropriate salary.	3.38	1.146
I receive appropriate benefits.	2.74	1.104
There is an appropriate difference between the pay awarded to good and bad performers.	2.62	1.109
I feel sense of Job satisfaction.	2.68	1.078
In general employees are adequately rewarded in my organization.	2.81	1.071
Everyone in my organization receives right salary.	3.35	1.142
Overall Mean/SD	2.87	1.101

Table III depicts the respondents' perception towards reward system available in their organization Neycer India Limited. The respondents are asked to rate their level of agreement towards reward system in five point scale. Mean and standard deviation values are calculated based on the collected data. The respondents have rated high for only two variables such as 'I receive an appropriate salary' and 'Everyone in my organization receives right salary' and they have rated very low for rest of the variables pertaining to the reward system of their organization. Further it is found from the Table 4.3 that the overall perception of the respondents towards the reward system is below average.

Table IV: Respondents' Perception towards Co-workers relationship

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation
I feel my efforts are valued by my peers.	2.63	1.107
Knowledge and information sharing is a group norm across the organization.	2.88	1.017
Employees consult each other when they need support.	2.51	1.021
Individuals appreciate the personal contribution of their peers.	2.72	1.094
When disagreements occur they are addressed promptly in order to resolve them.	2.86	1.079
Overall Mean/SD	2.72	1.063

Table IV presents the respondents' perception towards Co-workers relationship prevails in their organization Neycer India Limited. The respondents are asked to rate their level of agreement towards Co-workers relationship in five point scale. Mean and standard deviation values are calculated based on the collected data. The respondents have rated high for only two variables such as 'Knowledge and information sharing is a group norm across the organization' and 'When disagreements occur they are addressed promptly in order to resolve them' and they have rated very low for rest of the variables pertaining to Co-workers relationship exists in their organization. Further it is found from the Table 4.12 that the overall perception of the respondents towards the Co-workers relationship is below average.

Table V: Respondents' Perception towards Work environment

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation
I feel proud to be an employee of this organization.	2.75	1.047
I enjoy being a part of my organization.	2.79	1.060
Employees have good balance between work and personal life.	2.87	1.107
Morale is high across the organization.	2.81	1.031
Employees speak well about this organization.	3.22	1.204
Overall Mean/SD	2.88	5.449

Table V shows the respondents' perception towards work environment of their organization Neycer India Limited. The respondents are asked to rate their level of agreement towards work environment in five point scale. Mean and standard deviation values are calculated based on the collected data. The respondents have rated high for only two variables such as 'Employee speak well about this organization' and 'Morale is high across the organization' they have rated very low for the rest of variables pertaining to work environment of their organization. Further it is found from the Table 4.5 that the overall perception of the respondents towards the work environment is below average.

FINDINGS

The Findings given below are the outcome of the analysis of the mean scores of the respondents' (employees of Neycer India Limited) perception towards various dimensions of organizational climate. This analysis helped the researcher to find out the employees' perception towards the organizational climate of their organization. The findings based on objectives are summarized below:

- Respondents belong to below 30 years of the age group have rated comparatively high for all variables of organizational climate.
- The female respondents have rated comparatively high for all variables of organization climate.
- The unmarried respondents have rated comparatively high for all variables of organization climate.
- Respondents belong to HSC & below have rated comparatively high for all variables of organizational climate.
- Respondents belong to worker category have rated comparatively high for all variables of organizational climate.

It is also found that the overall perception of the respondents towards the Organizational design, Reward system, Co-workers relationship and Work environment is low.

CONCLUSIONS

The research study titled “An Empirical Study on Organizational Climate in Neycer India Limited, Vadalur” carried out with the employees of different hierarchy of Neycer India Limited, Vadalur of Tamil Nadu State. The prime aim of the study is to find out the employees' perception towards the climate their organisation. The results of the study reveal various interesting findings. The major finding is that the chosen employees having different kinds of demographic characteristics have perceived differently towards the climate of their organization and the overall perception of the respondents towards the Organizational design, Reward system, Co-workers relationship and Work environment is low..

The results of the analysis and interpretations of the responses of the employees made the researcher to offer certain suggestions to the study organization Neycer India Limited. The summary of the suggestions is that this organization should take necessary measures and steps to improve its organizational climate in order to make each and every one of its employees satisfied and thereby it can enhance its productivity and reduce labour turn over.

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